

**Workshop on Artificial Intelligence Techniques for the Optimization of
Electric Power Distribution Systems
5 May 2022, Porto, Portugal**

**Offline Metaheuristic Parameterization using Sequential Model
Algorithm Configuration**

Vitor Oliveira¹, Tiago Pinto^{1,2} and Ruben Romero³

¹Instituto Superior de Engenharia do Porto

²Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro / INESC-TEC

³Department of Electrical Engineering, São Paulo State University – UNESP, Ilha Solteira, SP, Brazil

Abstract:

The difficulty in solving computationally, through exact methods, many of the problems of real life, makes the formulation of optimization solutions one of the fields most studied by the scientific community in the field of artificial intelligence. Complex optimization problems are often associated to large search spaces and consequent prohibitive execution times in finding the optimal results. This is especially relevant when dealing with dynamic real problems, such as those in the field of power and energy systems. Solving this type of problems requires new models to find near-optimal solutions in acceptable times, such as metaheuristic optimization algorithms. The performance of these algorithms is, however, hugely dependent on their correct tuning, including their configuration and parametrization. This is an arduous task, usually done through exhaustive experimentation. This work contributes to overcome this challenge by proposing the application of sequential model algorithm configuration, using Bayesian optimization with Gaussian process and Monte Carlo Markov Chain for the automatic configuration of a genetic algorithm. Results from the application of this model to an electricity market participation optimization problem show that the genetic algorithm automatic configuration enables identifying the ideal tuning of the model, reaching better results when compared to a manual configuration, at similar execution times.

Related References:

Pinto, T., Morais, H., Sousa, T.M., Sousa, T., Vale, Z., Praça, I., Faia, R., Pires, E.J.S.: Adaptive Portfolio Optimization for Multiple Electricity Markets Participation. *IEEE transactions on neural networks and learning systems*. 27, 1720–1733 (2016).

Lei, L., Liu, N.: Research on Optimization Performance of Nonlinear Function Based on Multigroup Genetic Algorithm. In: 2020 IEEE 20th International Conference on Communication Technology (ICCT). pp. 1498–1502 (2020).

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCT50939.2020.9295871>

Bergstra, J., Komer, B., Eliasmith, C., Yamins, D., Cox, D.D.: Hyperopt: a Python library for model selection and hyperparameter optimization. *Computational Science & Discovery*. 8, 14008 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1749-4699/8/1/014008>.

Snoek, J., Larochelle, H., Adams, R.P.: Practical Bayesian Optimization of Machine Learning Algorithms. In: *Proceedings of the 25th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems - Volume 2*. pp. 2951–2959. Curran Associates Inc., Red Hook, NY, USA (2012).

Nomura, M., Abe, K.: A Simple Heuristic for Bayesian Optimization with A Low Budget. *ArXiv. abs/1911.0*, (2019).